

The Global Climate Action pyramid and SWOT

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Abstract:

This paper aims to find ways to ensure the sustainability of global climate action. As a result of the research, a pyramid was designed to achieve sustainability for global climate action strategies, starting from the base that includes the necessary needs for implementing global climate action, through formulating some of the strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities (GCA-SWOT) facing global climate action, reaching the top of the GCA pyramid that includes sustainability in global climate action.

Key Words: Global Climate Action, COP, GCA-SWOT, GCA Pyramid.

JEL Classification: Q50; Q54.

1- Introduction

There is global interest in climate change, but despite this there is a delay in implementing the commitments related to global climate action that were made previous meeting of the Conference of the Parties (especially the current meeting COP 28). Therefore, we pose the following problem: **How can global climate action be implemented? and how do we ensure its sustainability in the coming decades?**

2- Global Climate Action (GCA) definition

Climate action defined by the Paris Agreement started by set targets for reaching net-zero GHGs emissions by 2050. (Uczak de Goes, Markocsan, & Gupta, 2022). Also; "Climate action" refers to individual-organizational efforts to reduce GHGs emissions and increase springiness to climate change impacts. (Gunasiri, et al., 2022). Moreover; "Climate action" refers to all activities lead the world transform its energy, industry, transport, food, agriculture and forestry systems to ensure that can limit global temperature rise than 1.5°C. ((UN, 2023); (SDGs.UN, 2023); (UNEP, 2023)). As a brief definition it can be said that "Climate action" is the 13th goal among the Seventeen sustainable development goals (SDGs), which refers to take urgent actions and activities to combat climate change and its impacts around the World.

In addition; Global climate action refers to collective efforts and initiatives taken by countries, organizations, communities, and individuals around the world to address the challenges of climate change and mitigate its impacts. It involves implementing measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, promoting sustainable practices, and adapting to the changing climate. (TWT, 2022)

Global Climate Action (GCA) include some key aspects as follows: International Agreements (The Paris Agreement); Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Reduction (Reduce emissions of greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O) through various means); Renewable Energy Transition (Shift towards renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal power); Carbon Pricing (Considering carbon pricing mechanisms, such as carbon taxes or cap-and-trade systems to put a price on carbon emissions); Adaptation and Resilience (Involves taking measures to reduce vulnerability to the impacts of climate change and build resilience. This includes implementing strategies to manage water resources, protect ecosystems, develop climate-resilient infrastructure, and enhance disaster preparedness); Awareness and Education (Raising awareness about climate change and promote sustainable lifestyles, eco-friendly practices, and the importance of reducing carbon footprints through education, outreach programs); International Cooperation and Funding (Taking responsibility for greenhouse gas emissions and participating in financing climate action, as well as reaching agreement on

how to finance the Loss and Damage Fund). (TWT, 2022)

So global climate action requires a sustained commitment from stakeholders in Worldwide to achieve the Net-Zero as long-term goal by 2050.

The Global Climate Action SWOT (GCA-SWOT) is designed to helping implementation previous COP agreements and in order to enhance collaboration on climate action to confront existing challenges and create real opportunities. The idea of (GCA-SWOT) is derived from the sustainability swot (sSWOT). (METZGER, PUTT DEL PINO, PROWITT, GOODWARD, & PERERA, 2012)

Figure 1. The sustainability SWOT

Source: (METZGER, PUTT DEL PINO, PROWITT, GOODWARD, & PERERA, 2012, p. 02)

Figure 2. The Global Climate Action sustainability (Pyramid and SWOT)

Source: Author

The Global Climate Action SWOT shown through following figure:

Figure 3. The Global Climate Action SWOT (GCA-SWOT)

Source: Author

To ensure the sustainability of global climate action and reach the top of the pyramid, must:

1. Building a solid and strong base by: identifying all needs to achieve climate action (such as: the role of education in climate action, providing the necessary means and equipment, increasing the number of actors, providing funding, etc.)

2. Working within the SWOT of global climate action as follows:

➤ **Internally:** identifying the weaknesses in each country, region, city, or company and how to find remedial solutions for them to become strengths, as well as strengthening the existing internal strengths to expand the work externally.

➤ **Externally:** Identifying all threats and how to confront them to become opportunities through mitigation and adaptation strategies

The transition from weaknesses to strengths occurs through finding solutions to existing problems and answers to the questions raised regarding the weaknesses. As for the transition from threats to opportunities, it occurs through: Knowing the real threats and arranging them according to priority in confrontation, identifying possible opportunities in the field of climate action, linking the two strategies "Mitigation and adaptation", Scientific & technological Cooperation, and mobilizing the necessary funds.

3. After achieving the previous stages, ensuring the continuation of global climate action can be achieved through: Providing technological and financial support; Encouraging existing initiatives; Climate taxation; Spreading peace in all regions.

Conclusion

Achieving sustainability in global climate action requires starting from the base of the pyramid, which includes the basic needs of climate action, through studying each of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT), all the way to the top of the pyramid, which ensures continuity in global climate action.

There is no doubt that all countries have become aware of the threat of climate changes and the importance of global climate action, but the issue of how to implement commitments and the period of their implementation remain two problems facing progress in global climate action, which opens the way for future research topics.

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